

A Natural Language Processing based approach to automate the maintenance work order prioritization process: Understanding sentiments in context-aware systems

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ABSTRACT

The maintenance-related work order prioritization process at the Military Sealift Command (MSC) is highly influenced by the subjective experience of chief and shore-based engineering personnel. This interpretation continuum lies in the manual and time-consuming process of recreating the worldview of that situation/context and understanding the hidden sentiments in the data. This study proposes research on a conceptual framework based on sentiment analysis to reduce subjectivity in the work order prioritization process. The work is focused on developing an NLP (Natural Language Processing) based sentiment analysis model tailored for MSC's predictive maintenance program. The proposed model will prioritize the work orders from the highest negative score to the lowest one. In this context, a higher negativity score will indicate a greater sense of urgency and vice versa. This approach would automate the prioritization of maintenance records within MSC, enhancing interpretational efficiency and contributing to informed decision-making. It considers the pre-compiled manual and automatic reports as input. The framework would be developed through a structured process: Data Processing, Algorithm Development, and Validation & Verification. This paper focuses on the Data Processing of the compiled reports through a pre-trained model-based study to segregate and cluster maintenance-related lexicons. The model will be verified experimentally by comparing it with existing maintenance reports and conducting interviews with MSC's Subject Matter Experts. The project doesn't only aim to enhance interpretational efficiency but also contributes towards informed decision-making and improved operational performance.

INTRODUCTION

For MSC, like many other organizations, the seamless operation of facilities and equipment heavily depends on the efficient management of maintenance work orders. Traditionally, the detection and reporting of technical issues in MSC have largely relied on manual inputs by technicians, field engineers, survey

engineers, and other staff. These employees create manual reports, known as, Engineering Status Report, which are then stored on SAMM (Shipboard Automated Maintenance Management) (Afloat); software developed by MSC. However, this software currently does not utilize primary run-to-failure data effectively, which tracks equipment performance up to the point of failure, could be crucial in establishing proactive maintenance strategies. This process is dependent on shore based engineering personnel knowledge and experience, creating a risk regarding subjectivity and inconsistency between what is captured on the ship and what the shore-based engineering personnel infers from their reports. Therefore, there exists a requirement to restructure the process of prioritizing maintenance work orders and shift towards a method that is characterized by a more methodical, predictive, and data-centric approach. In MSC's dynamic environment, automation can facilitate optimum facility and equipment operation, and reduce unscheduled downtime. (Ensafi et al., 2023).

BACKGROUND

The Naval Safety Center has reported that approx. 6% of advanced machine failures are related to the maintenance (Naval Safety Center, n.d.). The primary issues are identified as a lack of trained staff, scheduling conflicts, and limited maintenance resources (US Government Accountability Office, 2022a). Current research identifies the root cause of such issues related to human factors, performance, performance measurements, and resource management (Peach et al., 2016). Exploring the current techniques adopted by US Defense, the DuoPoint and the Swiss Cheese are the models predominantly followed today (Naval Safety Center, n.d.). Despite the continuous efforts to improve, the US Navy has reported an approx. \$1.8 billion maintenance backlog, resulting in heavy losses (US Government Accountability Office, 2022b). The unaccounted-for gaps causing these losses are part of a "system" incorporating human comprehension, writing, reading, and understanding of maintenance reports, as revealed by examining the

techniques and concerns the US Navy raised. It has been acknowledged in other industries that maintenance-related documentation causes failures; in fact, 6% of total HITL - Human in the Loop failures are related to poor documentation (Hawwach, 2021; Morag, 2018).

The current process described in Figure 1. how data collection, reporting, and management system, is then used for decision-making by the shore-based engineering personnel. The figure shows the process of decision-making by shore based engineering personnel by analyzing the reports on SAMM.

In Figure 1, the current *operational environment* represents the real-world scenario where ship “maintenance” is required. In the data collection stage, most data are done manually by ground technicians, field engineers, survey engineers, and others. In some instances, the data is collected using a handheld device that collects the data over IoT sensors onboard the ship and automatically generates a report based on the pre-trained standardized templates. In the case of manual data recordings, the reports are generated by personnel by interpreting the recorded data. Manual and automatic reports are then compiled into SAMM Afloat, where the database management system re-organizes them based on the pre-established framework. The ship’s data/reports replicate to SAMM ashore, a shoreside version of the SAMM program. The reports are condensed into Engineering Status Reports, which are then interpreted by the shore-based engineering personnel and sectional heads to manage inventory.

The prioritization process involves “interpreting” the situation or reports manually several times. While the data points provide objective characteristics, manual reporting is very subjective. Additionally, the shore-based engineering personnel must re-create the context of reporting, interpret the reports, and make a reliable and accurate decision – the subjective behavior in each step involves either losing critical information or misinterpreting the operational need.

Figure 1: As-Is State of the MSC Work Orders Prioritization Process

The challenge of this process is that it lacks the ability to “preserve” the notion, context, and sentiment of human understanding while writing, reporting, and understanding the intent from one stage to another. The current process loses the human context in the data sequence resulting in varied technical or maintenance reports. The goal is to comprehend these reports in their entirety while “preserving” the intended context from the writer/reporter.

METHODOLOGY

The study suggests the implementation of a natural language processing (NLP) technique commonly known as “sentiment analysis” to the data management process of maintenance records. Figure 2a shows the addition of this capability to the existing MSC prioritization process. This technique has been actively deployed in Socio-Technical Systems (STS), i.e., systems where both humans and machines play key roles (Heredia et al., 2016, Javadnejad et al., 2022, Lynch et al., 2021, Grigoryan, 2022). However, the challenging part of sentiment analysis is mapping the objective elements of the component to subjective ones embedded in human comprehension.

As shown in Figure 2a, the new proposed approach introduces an Artificial Intelligence (A.I.) model after generating the reports. The manual and automated reports are fed as inputs which convert the “subjective” relations to the “objective” ranking of the components. This is provided to the shore-based engineering personnel for comparison with the compiled reports from SAMM where the shore-based engineering personnel can make a determination on the best course of action. Although outside the scope of this study a follow-on task would be to introduce this technology into SAMM eliminating the dual paths, providing the

shore-based engineering personnel with the AI generated reports exclusively (figure 2b).

Figure 2a: To-Be State of Sentimental A.I. Injection for the MSC Work Orders Prioritization Process

Figure 2b: To-Be State of the MSC Work Orders Prioritization Process

Introducing Sentimental A.I. in the maintenance work order prioritization process has many advantages. Specifically, it adds quality, unambiguity, and objectivity to the decision-making process while substantially reducing time, subjectivity, and loss of contextual information. The critical advantage is that the machine learns and preserves the expertise of the port engineers over time. Hence, the MSC does not lose information or experience with retiring port engineers.

Selecting the appropriate sentiment level and type is a significant process to adapt sentiment analysis to the ship maintenance domain successfully. Sentiment level is the granularity at which sentiment is analyzed, while sentiment type is the approach used to analyze the sentiment. The different granularities at which sentiment analysis can be performed are the document, sentence, and aspect-level analysis (Balaji et al., 2017). The types of sentiment analysis include lexicon-based, machine learning-based, and hybrid approaches (Wankhade et al., 2022). This study aims to employ an

aspect-level machine learning-based sentiment analysis. The Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) goes beyond the overall sentiment of a document and identifies the sentiment toward specific aspects or entities within the text (Mowlaei et al., 2020). By focusing on aspects (e.g., specific attributes or components of a ship), ABSA can provide more detailed and actionable insights compared to traditional sentiment analysis. Machine learning-based sentiment analysis can potentially identify subtle or complex sentiment expressions that indicate potential issues or maintenance needs over traditional, rule-based approaches (Birjali et al., 2021). Following that, the proposed sentimental model will be trained to recognize maintenance-specific language and terminology, ensuring its applicability and usefulness within the context of ship maintenance.

By interpreting the intent of maintenance work order descriptions, the proposed novel model will attribute a score to each ship component in the work orders, reflecting the urgency of the request. The scores will be assigned regarding the “sentiment orientation” of the failure descriptions (Taboada et al., 2011). Sentiment orientation has two elements: “sentiment polarity” (positive, negative, and neutral) and “sentiment strength” (power of the polarity indicated with scores). The prioritization of work orders will be determined by ranking these negativity scores from highest to lowest, allowing maintenance teams to promptly resolve the most urgent problems and allocate resources most effectively. In this context, a higher negativity score will indicate a greater sense of urgency, while a lower negativity score will indicate a lesser sense of urgency.

For example, the severity level of the failure descriptions in these two following sentences are different from each other: “This engine is broken down!” and “This engine is leaking!” The first sentence should have a higher negative score resulting from a more severe failure description that will quite likely have a more significant impact on the engine’s functionality. For another example, let’s presume that the “propulsion system” is more vital to ship operations than the “fuel system”. The severity level of the failure descriptions in the following two sentences differs: “The propulsion system has failed!” and “The fuel system has failed!”. The first sentence should have a higher negative score since its failure description is more grievous and will likely have a greater impact on the engine’s functionality.

The proposed unique sentiment analysis model can change the human manual annotation application in

prioritization process and foster a more proactive and data-driven approach to data management through the strategic application of advanced A.I. and NLP techniques.

FUTURE WORK

Sentiment Analysis presents the possibility of mapping subjective elements to “generalize” objective scores to translate human understanding into machine-readable anecdotes. This individual piece of research must be accompanied by semantic analysis to understand the pre-cursor and post-cursor of a phrase/statement/query etc. The bridge required to connect sentiment and semantic analysis is “context vector mapping.” Other helpful techniques include Attention Mechanism. The scope of this research begins only after a “standardized” report is generated. There is a significant challenge in addressing the data collection and transcribing the data into reports. There are uncertainties in data management within the quantitative realm, where human factors do not realize the misinterpretation due to tacit knowledge or situational complicacies.

Figure 3: Future To-Be State of the MSC autonomous Ship Inspection and work order management

This research has the potential to extend its impact for complete autonomy of ship inspection and placing orders for required components. This is represented in Figure 3. It starts with the standard process of Industrial 3.0 – autonomous data collection using sensors. A meticulously curated and trained Large Language Model (LLM) for MSC will generate reports based on defined templates. The context of ship maintenance forms the core of the template. Hence the output of the generative A.I. will be contextually rich and accurate (Yang et al., 2023). In the third stage, the current research work on the sentimental A.I. and semantic A.I. will be integrated into SAMM (onboard - Afloat the ship and ashore/cloud version) to generate an objective score based on ranking on the RUL of components.

CONCLUSION

The novelty of this research is in the application of NLP sentiment analysis to tackle the issue of manual maintenance work order prioritization. The concept aims to enhance efficiency, minimize unnecessary maintenance efforts, prolong the operational lifespan of assets, and save expenses by leveraging run-to-failure data. The proposed data-driven solution has the potential to have far-reaching effects and profoundly alter the maintenance management environment. Reducing the port engineer's manual work, likelihood of making errors, and inconsistency in interpretations of the maintenance records is of great benefit.

The cloud plays an important role in syncing the data in real time. However, a backup transfer can be made to the SAMM Ashore module if necessary. The fourth stage is focused on placing orders and inventory checks for replacements using smart contracts. This will eliminate the possibility of biases for preferred contractors while keeping a check on over-stocking or under-stocking spare parts. As all “systems” are not perfect, feedback/control or tuning is required to improve the proposed “system.” The feedback loop is auto-generated through failure mode analysis at each node of command execution. This is a part of causal A.I., as mentioned in the figure. However, certain environmental factors, such as policy changes or the introduction of disruptive technology (ex: a new material innovation), cannot be learned by this settled-up A.I. “system” (Ganguly et al., 2023; Kıcıman et al., 2023). Other relevant decision-making still needs human interference (Subject Matter Experts). These will form a part of the feedback loop for the generative A.I. model to learn and adapt to further increase contextual awareness.

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